

1 **Effect of Milking Interval on Milk Secretion and Mammary Tight Junction**

2 **Permeability in Dairy Ewes**

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ABSTRACT

13 Twenty-four lactating ewes (Manchega, **MN**; n = 12, and Lacaune, **LC**; n = 12) in
14 mid-lactation were used to assess the effect of different machine milking intervals (4, 8, 12,
15 16, 20 and 24 h) on milk yield, milk composition, and tight junction (TJ) permeability of
16 mammary epithelial cells, in a short-period trial. Milk samples were analyzed for composition
17 (fat, protein, casein, true protein, lactose, and total solids), somatic cell count (SCC), and
18 plasmin activity. Milk accumulated linearly up to 24 h in both breeds, showing a milk
19 accumulation rate of 37.52 and 86.63 mL/h in MN and LC ewes, respectively. Milking
20 interval affected significantly percentage of fat, which decreased markedly from 4- to 24-h
21 milking interval in both breeds, but no differences were observed in protein content. Casein,
22 true protein, lactose and total solids contents varied with milking interval. MN and LC ewes
23 presented low levels of SCC in all the milking intervals tested (138 to 339 and 112 to 191×10³
24 cells/mL, respectively), showing that udder health was not adversely affected by different
25 milking intervals. Plasmin activity was significantly affected by milking interval, increasing
26 until 20 h of udder filling in both breeds. Moreover, plasmin activity in milk was positively
27 correlated with SCC content (r = 0.39), indicating a greater plasmin activity in the milk with
28 high SCC. Plasma lactose, milk Na⁺ and milk K⁺ concentrations were used as indicators of TJ
29 permeability. Plasma lactose began to increase rapidly after 20 h of milk accumulation, and
30 indicated enhanced permeability of mammary TJ in MN and LC dairy ewes. In MN ewes, an
31 increase in Na⁺ concentration and Na⁺ to K⁺ ratio, and a decrease in K⁺ concentration were
32 observed in milk. No differences in the ion concentration in milk of LC ewes were observed
33 despite of TJ leakiness. Our results suggest that MN and LC dairy sheep could produce
34 normal levels of milk yield during short-periods of extended milking intervals with no
35 negative effects on milk yield or udder health. Nevertheless, increases in TJ permeability after

36 20 h of udder filling seem to favor changes in milk composition, being more marked in MN
37 than in LC breed.

38 (**Keywords:** milking frequency, tight junctions, milk production, dairy sheep)

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INTRODUCTION

41 The Southern European countries around the Mediterranean Basin (Cyprus, France,
42 Greece, Italy, Spain and Portugal) are the most important producers of sheep milk. They
43 produce about 27% of the world sheep milk production (FAO, 2004) and more than 80-90%
44 of the sheep milk collected by dairies in the world comes from this area (Dubeuf and Le
45 Jaouen, 2005). Moreover, nearly all the sheep milk production is processed in cheese, which
46 is in increasing demand throughout the world and represents a high source of value creation
47 for sheep milk. Therefore, sheep milk is becoming a really interesting alternative for farmers.
48 Most of the dairy-sheep farmers maintain large flocks and practice twice-daily milking
49 throughout lactation. As a result, a high percentage of the total labor (about 55%; Marnet and
50 McKusick, 2001) is spent in milking. Thus, the milking is becoming one of the main
51 handicaps to encourage people to produce sheep milk.

52 The use of extended milking intervals could result in significant reductions in labor
53 and time spent in the milking parlor. McKusick et al. (2002) described a reduction of
54 approximately 27% of total parlor time when ewes were milked 3 times in 48 h instead of
55 twice daily. Nevertheless, some studies show that decreasing the number of daily milkings in
56 dairy ewes reduce milk yield by 18 to 30% and modify milk composition (Morag, 1968;
57 Labussière et al., 1974; Nudda et al., 2002).

58 The tight junctions (**TJ**; zonulae occludentes) form an important part of the junctional
59 complex between adjacent epithelial cells and also between endothelial cells. They are semi-
60 permeable extracellular structures surrounding each cell in a “gasket-like” manner in close

61 proximity to the apical domain of the cell. When intact, they act as a barrier between adjacent
62 epithelial and endothelial cells, thus preventing paracellular transport of ions and small
63 solutes, and maintaining an electrochemical gradient (Stelwagen et al., 1995). In the
64 mammary gland, it was shown that the permeability of TJ can be increased during established
65 lactation if extended milking intervals are performed. In cows, TJ switch to a leaky state after
66 approximately 17 h of milk accumulation in cows (Stelwagen et al., 1997) and after 21 h in
67 goats (Stelwagen et al., 1994b), allowing the movement of milk components into the
68 interstitial fluid and vice versa (Stelwagen et al., 1997). Furthermore, this increase in
69 permeability is associated with a decrease in milk yield (Stelwagen et al., 1995), in milk
70 secretion (Stelwagen et al., 1994b; Stelwagen et al., 1997), and with an increase in protease
71 activity in milk (Stelwagen et al., 1994c). Plasmin (**PL**), a serine-proteinase, appears to be the
72 predominant responsible of protease activity in milk, and it is mainly associated to CN
73 micelles, which represent its substrate (Bastian and Brown, 1996). Stelwagen et al. (1994c)
74 and Kelly et al. (1998) reported significant increments in the activity of PL in milk during
75 extended milking intervals, indicating that paracellular leakage may contribute to increased
76 protease activity during less frequent milking. Thus, losses of mammary TJ integrity may not
77 only compromise milk secretion but also may affect milk quality.

78 The purpose of the present study was twofold: first, to evaluate the effects of different
79 milking intervals on milk yield, milk composition, and udder health in 2 different dairy ewe
80 breeds differing in their capacity of milk production (Manchega and Lacaune), and, second, to
81 assess whether extended milking intervals may open mammary TJ in dairy ewes.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

84 The experimental procedures and animal care conditions were approved by the Ethical
85 Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de
86 Barcelona (reference CEEAH 02/410).

87 *Animals and Management Conditions*

88 Twelve Manchega (**MN**) and 12 Lacaune (**LC**) lactating ewes with symmetrical and
89 healthy udders, in their second to fourth lactation, from the experimental farm of SGCE
90 (Servei de Granges i Camps Experimentals) of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona in
91 Bellaterra, were used in a 2-wk (wk 11 and 16) trial.

92 Ewes were chosen on the basis of milk yield and SCC. Before the beginning of the
93 experiment (wk 10), average daily milk yields were 1.1 ± 0.09 L and 2.3 ± 0.11 L in
94 Manchega and Lacaune, respectively, and SCC were inferior to 200,000 cells/mL.
95 Furthermore, chosen ewes were bacteriologically tested in order to confirm that udders were
96 healthy.

97 The animals were allocated at wk 10 and 15 of lactation into 6 groups of 4 ewes each
98 (MN, n = 2; and LC, n = 2). Moreover, they were housed separated from the main flock, in
99 order to avoid spontaneous secretion of endogenous oxytocin as a consequence of the milking
100 machine noise. Ewes received constant illumination to diminish diurnal and nocturnal milk
101 secretion differences. They were offered a mixture of dehydrated alfalfa and fescue hay fed ad
102 libitum, and were supplemented with 800 g daily of concentrate mixture pellets.

103 Ewes were milked in a double-12 stall parallel milking parlor (Westfalia Surge
104 Ibérica, Granollers, Spain) equipped with recording jars and low-line milk pipeline. Milking
105 was performed at a vacuum pressure of 42 kPa, a pulsation rate of 120 pulses/min, and a
106 pulsation ratio of 50%. The milking routine for the regular daily milkings (08.00 and 18.00)
107 included machine milking without udder preparation or teat cleaning, machine stripping, and
108 teat dipping in an iodine solution (P3-cide plus, Henkel Hygiene, Barcelona, Spain).

109 *Experimental procedures*

110 The experimental design was a crossover with 6 milking intervals (4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and
111 24 h) at random and repeated measurements (wk 11 and 16). The milking intervals were
112 randomly applied successively without any period of washing-out between them. At the end
113 of the milking of d 1 (0 h) and after each milking performed during the experiment, ewes
114 were injected i.v. with 2 IU of oxytocin (Veterin Lobulor, Laboratorios Andreu, Barcelona,
115 Spain) to remove the residual milk in the udder, assuring the udder emptying. One of the 6
116 milking interval treatments was then randomly applied. Each group was exposed to a different
117 order of treatments application to avoid possible carryover effects between experimental
118 milking intervals.

119 *Sampling and Analyses*

120 Milk yield was recorded and milk samples were taken at each milking. For analysis of
121 milk composition, a sample of approximately 100 mL was collected and preserved with
122 $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (0.3 g/L) at 4 °C. Unhomogenized milk samples were analyzed with a near infrared
123 spectrometer (Technicon InfraAlyzer-450, Bran+Luebbe SL, Nordersted, Germany), using the
124 method of Albanell et al. (1999), for contents of TS, fat, protein ($N \times 6.38$), true protein, CN,
125 and lactose. For SCC, samples were preserved with an anti-microbial tablet (Bronopol, Broad
126 Spectrum Micro-tabs II, D&F Control Systems Inc., San Ramon, CA) and kept at 4 °C until
127 analysis. The SCC was determined in the Dairy Herd Improvement Laboratory of Catalonia
128 (ALLIC, Cabrils, Barcelona, Spain) using an automatic cell counter (Fossomatic 5000, Foss
129 Electric, Hillerød, Denmark).

130 The concentrations of Na^+ and K^+ in milk and of lactose in plasma were used as
131 indicators of the leakiness of TJ (Stelwagen et al., 1995; Stelwagen et al., 1997). Total milk
132 samples (10 mL) from each milking interval were collected and frozen at -20 °C until analysis
133 for Na^+ and K^+ content by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-

134 AES) in the Chemical Analysis Service of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
135 (Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain). To determine concentrations of plasma lactose, blood samples
136 (10 mL) of 8 experimental ewes (MN, n = 4, and LC, n = 4) were collected into heparinized
137 tubes (Venoject, Terumo Europe, Belgium) from the jugular vein by venipuncture for each
138 milking-interval treatment and were stored at 4 °C until centrifugation at $490 \times g$ for 15 min.
139 Plasma was collected and stored at -20 °C until the analysis of lactose in the Veterinary
140 Clinical Biochemistry Service of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Bellaterra,
141 Barcelona, Spain), according to the method described by Stelwagen et al. (1994a).

142 Milk samples only from the first experimental period (wk 11) were immediately
143 frozen and stored at -80 °C until the analysis of plasmin activity. Plasmin activity was
144 determined with the method described by Baldi et al. (1996). Assays were performed in
145 duplicate in 250 μ L of 0.1 M Tris-HCL buffer (pH 7.4), 0.6 mM Val-Leu-Lys-p-nitroanilide
146 (Bachem AG, Bubendorf, Switzerland) and 30 μ L of the milk supernatant. The reaction
147 mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 3 h and A_{405} was recorded at 30-min intervals. A sample
148 without supernatant served as a control for the detection of spontaneous breakdown of the
149 substrate. The rate of p-nitroanilide formation was calculated from the linear portion of the
150 absorbance versus time curve. Plasmin was expressed as units, one unit being the amount of
151 enzyme that produces a change in absorbance at 405 nm of 0.1 in 60 min.

152 *Statistical Analyses*

153 Data were analyzed by the PROC MIXED procedure for repeated measurements of
154 SAS (SAS 8.2; SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC). The mixed model used included the fixed effects of
155 milking interval (4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24 h), breed (MN and LC), group (1 to 6), period (wk
156 11 and 16), and order of treatment application (1st to 6th); the random effect of animal nested
157 within the group and breed; and the interactions between breed and milking interval, period
158 and milking interval, plus the residual error. Plasmin activity analysis did not include the

159 effect of period and their interactions in the model. Differences between least square means
 160 were determined with the PDIFF test of SAS. Pearson's correlation coefficients between
 161 measurements were also calculated. Significance was declared as $P < 0.05$ unless otherwise
 162 indicated.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

165 *Milk Yield and Milk Secretion Rate*

166 Breed and period affected ($P < 0.001$) milk yield. Milk yield of MN ewes was lower
 167 than LC ewes (averaged across all intervals, 533 vs. 1227 mL, respectively). It is clear that
 168 both breeds have different potentiality to produce milk as previously described by other
 169 authors (Such et al., 1995; Rovai, 2001). Average milk yields in the first experimental period
 170 (wk 11) were greater ($P < 0.05$) than in the second period (wk 16) in both breeds (MN: 623
 171 vs. 444 mL; LC: 1339 vs. 1150 mL, respectively). Our results agree with those of Rovai
 172 (2001), who showed a significant diminution in daily milk yield as lactation advanced, for the
 173 same breeds.

174 Milk production was also affected ($P < 0.001$) by the milking interval performed, and
 175 accumulated linearly ($P < 0.05$) up to 24 h in MN and LC breeds (Table 1). Accumulation of
 176 milk production was described by the following equations (average of both experimental
 177 periods):

178 MN: Milk yield (mL) = $37.521 \times$ time after udder emptying (h); $R^2 = 0.9839$

179 LC: Milk yield (mL) = $86.634 \times$ time after udder emptying (h); $R^2 = 0.9918$

180 The lineal milk accumulation pattern obtained in MN and LC breeds agrees with
 181 earlier observations in dairy ewes (McKusick et al., 2002) and dairy goats (Salama et al.,
 182 2004), where different milking intervals were also applied in short-term periods.

183 As shown in Table 1, milk accumulation rate depends on the breed ($P < 0.001$) being
184 greater in LC than in MN breed (86.6 vs. 37.5 mL/h; $P < 0.05$). In addition, the lineal milk
185 accumulation was faster ($P < 0.05$) in wk 11 (MN: 44.3 and LC: 94.5 mL/h) than in wk 16
186 (MN: 31.2 and LC: 79.2 mL/h), indicating that the speed of milk secretion decreased
187 throughout lactation. In both breeds, milk secretion rate reached the greatest value at 8-h
188 milking interval and the lowest one at 20 to 24 h of udder filling, indicating a secretion rate
189 saturation effect with time, as reported in dairy ewes (McKusick et al., 2002), goats (Peaker
190 and Blatchford, 1988; Salama et al., 2003), and cows (Knight et al., 1994; Davis et al., 1998;
191 Ayadi et al., 2003). The reduction of milk secretion rate, after reaching the maximum value,
192 was more marked ($P < 0.05$) in MN than in LC ewes (-20% and -11%, respectively, from 8 to
193 20-h milking interval). These differences could indicate that LC ewes tolerate extended
194 milking intervals better than MN ewes.

195 In order to study milk secretion with more precision, we calculated milk secretion rate
196 throughout each 4-h milking interval (Figure 1). In both breeds milk secretion rate had the
197 greatest value from 4 to 8 h (MN: 51 ml/h, LC: 112 mL/h) and decreased as time after udder
198 emptying increased. The lowest milk secretion values (MN: 27 mL/h, LC: 73 mL/h) were
199 obtained between 16- and 20-h milking interval. Extended milking intervals in the present
200 experiment were performed for short periods, and milk yield losses may be associated with
201 changes in the TJ permeability and increments of intra-alveolar pressure (Stelwagen et al.,
202 2001). Milk yield losses as a consequence of TJ permeability were observed after 17 h of milk
203 accumulation in dairy cows (Stelwagen et al., 1997), and after 21 h in dairy goats (Stelwagen
204 et al., 1994b). Also, the increase in the concentration of the putative feedback inhibitor of
205 lactation, synthesized by the mammary gland (Wilde et al., 1995), may play a role in the milk
206 secretion diminution 16 h after milking.

207 Although lower milk secretion rates were expected in ewes milked between 20- and
208 24-h milking interval, our results (Figure 1) showed an increase in milk secretion rate in MN
209 (+115%, $P < 0.05$) and LC (+25%, $P = 0.06$), compared to the previous 4 h (16 to 20 h). This
210 increment seems to be contradictory because impairment of mammary TJ integrity is
211 associated with decreased milk secretion during an extended milking interval (Stelwagen et
212 al., 1994b). This phenomenon has not been reported previously in dairy ewes. We
213 hypothesize that disrupted intercellular junctions might allow an influx of the interstitial fluid
214 into milk, generating the “apparent milk” secretion increase observed from 20- to 24-h
215 milking interval in both breeds. This increase in milk yield after TJ opening is in agreement
216 with an increase of milk secretion rate in dairy goats after inducing the disruption of
217 mammary TJ with the use of ethylene glycol-tetraacetic acid (Stelwagen et al., 1995).

218 Although the entrance of interstitial fluid into milk occurred in both breeds, the
219 increase in milk secretion rate between 20- and 24-h intervals was less evident in LC than in
220 MN ewes. Udders with large cisterns produce more milk and are more tolerant to longer
221 milking intervals in dairy ewes (Labussière, 1988; Rovai et al., 2001), dairy goats (Peaker and
222 Blatchford, 1988; Salama et al., 2003) and dairy cows (Knight and Dewhurst, 1994).
223 Therefore, damages of intercellular junctions, and probably of mammary epithelial cells,
224 might be less evident in LC ewes, which are characterized by large cistern volume and greater
225 cistern milk fraction than MN ewes (68% vs. 53%, $P < 0.05$, respectively, Rovai, 2001).

226 ***Milk Composition***

227 Milk component percentages (Table 2) were influenced by the breed ($P < 0.001$),
228 except lactose. These results agree with Rovai (2001), who reported that milk of MN contains
229 more fat and protein than milk of LC.

230 Milking interval affected ($P < 0.05$) percentages of fat, CN, true protein, lactose and
231 TS. Milk fat percentage was the most affected component in both breeds. Milk fat content

232 decreased ($P < 0.05$) with longer milking intervals. These results are in accordance with the
233 previous observations of McKusick et al. (2002) in a short-term experiment in dairy ewes.
234 Changes in fat content may be related to differing regulatory mechanisms for secretion of
235 milk fat globules relative to the components in the aqueous phase of milk (Davis et al., 1999).

236 Milking interval did not affect protein percentage in milk of MN and LC breeds,
237 which contrasts with data obtained in East Friesian ewes, where milk protein increased as
238 milking interval increased (McKusick et al., 2002).

239 The CN does not move through leaky mammary TJ, presumably because of the large
240 size of their micelles (Stelwagen et al., 1998a). Thus, while milk volume augmented with
241 longer milking intervals, CN synthesized remained constant in the milk, as in LC ewes.
242 However, in Manchega ewes, the lowest CN content was observed when the shortest milking
243 interval was performed (4 h). It seems that CN secretion in MN breed starts at slower rate
244 than milk secretion. Furthermore, the decrease of CN content observed at 24-h milking
245 interval in MN could be due to the opening of TJ from 20 h, allowing the entrance of large
246 quantity of intercellular fluid into milk and resulting in the dilution of CN.

247 In both breeds, true protein contents increased with milking interval, reaching the
248 greatest value at 20-h milking interval and stabilized thereafter. True protein in milk contains
249 the proteins synthesized in the mammary gland (e.g., CN) and the serum proteins entering the
250 milk when mammary TJ are disrupted. Therefore, in our experiment, the increase in true
251 protein content at extended milking intervals was likely due to an increment in serum proteins
252 in milk because of the loss of mammary TJ integrity. The entrance of serum proteins (e.g.,
253 serum albumin) into milk as a consequence of mammary TJ disruption was previously
254 observed in dairy cows milked once daily (Stelwagen et al., 1994a; Stelwagen et al. 1997).

255 Milk fat was low at longer milking intervals and milk protein did not vary, which
256 contradicts results obtained from long-term experiments, where reducing milking frequency

257 from 2 to 1 milking daily resulted in greater fat and protein contents in all breeds of ewes
258 tested: Tsigay, Karagouniko, Lacaune, Sarda, Manchega, and Churra (Labussière, 1983) and
259 Sarda, Awassi, and Merino (Nudda et al., 2002). Milking intervals tested in the current study
260 were performed for short periods, which may explain the discrepancy between short- and
261 long-term studies. When extended milking interval is performed for long period, animal
262 adapts for this situation by decreasing milk yield and concentrating milk components.

263 Lactose content was lowest ($P < 0.05$) at the 24-h milking interval in MN and LC
264 ewes. Such result is in agreement with previous findings in Awassi and Merino ewes (Nudda
265 et al., 2002), where a decrease in lactose content was observed in animals exposed to once
266 daily milking for a short period. Lactose in milk of MN ewes decreased (-3%, $P < 0.05$) from
267 20- to 24-h milking interval, whereas in LC ewes did not vary (-1.5%). Decreases of milk
268 lactose percentage seem to be due to lactose passing from milk into blood through impaired
269 TJ (Stelwagen et al., 1994a, 1994b, and 1995) associated with extended milking intervals.

270 As milking interval increased, the yield of milk components (fat, protein, lactose and
271 TS) augmented significantly in both breeds in accordance with the increase in milk yield (data
272 not shown).

273 Milk SCC was not affected ($P > 0.10$) by breed. The MN and LC ewes showed a low
274 level of SCC at all milking intervals tested (211 and 144×10^3 cells/mL, respectively),
275 indicating that sheep udders were healthy (González-Rodríguez et al., 1995) and not affect by
276 performing different milking intervals in a short period. Nevertheless, milk SCC values
277 (Table 2) varied ($P < 0.001$) with milking interval. The greatest logSCC in milk was observed
278 at 8-h milking interval in MN and at 8 to 12 in LC, probably due to a concentration effect.
279 Our results are in agreement with other studies conducted in dairy ewes (McKusick et al.,
280 2002; Luiz Ramellas et al., 2003) and dairy goats (Salama et al., 2003), where milk obtained
281 at short milking intervals had greater logSCC.

282 ***Plasmin Activity***

283 The PL activity was similar in both breeds (Figure 2) and averaged 6.90 ± 0.86
284 units/mL in MN and 5.15 ± 1.24 units/mL in LC. Our data are lower than those found for
285 ovine milk in previous studies (Chiofalo et al., 1999; Bianchi et al., 2004; Albenzio et al.,
286 2005). These differences could be at least partially explained by diversity of SCC levels and
287 stages of lactation of the animals used in each experiment, since PL activity in ewes' milk
288 was reported to be markedly affected by SCC and stage of lactation (Albenzio et al., 2004;
289 Bianchi et al., 2004; Albenzio et al., 2005).

290 Milking interval affected ($P < 0.05$) PL activity in MN and LC ewes' milk, which is in
291 agreement with results shown in dairy cows by Stelwagen et al. (1994c) and Kelly et al.
292 (1998), where the diminution of milking frequency incremented significantly PL activity.
293 However, Klei et al. (1997) and O'Brien et al. (2002) did not find significant effects of
294 different milking frequencies on PL concentrations in dairy cows.

295 In MN and LC, PL activity increased with milking interval up to 20 h and stabilized
296 thereafter. The PL activity may be augmented either by increasing leakage from blood or by
297 conversion of plasminogen to plasmin (Politis et al., 1989). It appears likely that, in our study,
298 the increase in PL activity is the result of an enhanced influx of enzyme from the blood to the
299 milk across damaged TJ when extended milking intervals are performed (see discussion
300 below).

301 Correlations coefficients between PL and milk yield and milk composition were
302 calculated. A low and negative correlation was observed between milk yield and PL activity
303 ($r = -0.18$; $P < 0.05$). This can be related to the fact that ewes with higher milk yield usually
304 have larger cisterns and are more tolerant to longer milking intervals (Labussière, 1988; Rovai
305 et al., 2001). Therefore, it is possible that they don't suffer a high TJ leakiness and
306 consequently, the plasminogen and plasmin entrance from the blood into the milk is less

307 marked than in ewes with smaller cisterns. On the contrary, positive correlations were
308 observed between PL and SCC ($r = 0.39$; $P < 0.001$) in agreement with previous findings in
309 sheep (Albenzio et al., 2004), bovine (Politis et al., 1989; Bastian et al., 1991; Baldi et al.,
310 1996), and goat milk (Fantuz et al., 2001). Milk protein ($r = 0.40$; $P < 0.001$), CN ($r = 0.37$; P
311 < 0.001), and true protein ($r = 0.40$; $P < 0.001$) contents also correlated positively with PL
312 activity. It is well known that plasminogen and plasminogen activators are associated with CN
313 micelles (Richardson, 1983). Thus, it may be hypothesized that the higher the CN content, the
314 greater the amount of plasminogen activator that remain bound into the micelles and convert
315 the plasminogen to PL (Albenzio et al., 2004).

316 *Tight Junction Permeability*

317 Results described above suggest the impairment of TJ as one of the main causes of
318 variations in milk secretion rate and milk composition when extended milking intervals are
319 performed. In order to confirm this hypothesis, lactose concentration in plasma and mineral
320 concentration (Na^+ and K^+) in milk were used as indicators of the state of TJ (Table 3 and
321 Figure 3).

322 Lactose in plasma was considered the main indicator of mammary TJ permeability in
323 the present study because changes in Na^+ and K^+ concentrations may simply reflect an
324 alteration in the transport of these ions across transcellular rather than paracellular pathway.
325 Lactose is not produced in any organ other than the mammary gland (Khun and Linzell, 1970)
326 and it is not secreted basolaterally (Stelwagen et al., 1998a), so its presence in blood can only
327 be explained by its movement from milk into blood via leaky TJ. The use of plasma lactose as
328 a reliable indicator of TJ permeability has been extensively studied in dairy cows and goats
329 (Stelwagen et al. 1994b; Stelwagen et al. 1995; Stelwagen et al. 1997).

330 Our results did not show interbreed differences in lactose concentration in plasma
331 (MN: 7.21 and LC: 16.56 $\mu\text{mol/L}$; $P = 0.35$) because of the high variability.

332 Lactation period affected ($P < 0.05$) the concentration of lactose in plasma.
333 Concentration of lactose at wk 11 (16.69 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) was greater than at wk 16 (8.09 $\mu\text{mol/L}$).
334 In the first period, udder distention was greater than in the second one due to the elevated
335 milk production. This fact seemed to favor the TJ impairment during this period.

336 Milking interval affected ($P < 0.01$) lactose concentration in plasma (Figure 3). In
337 both breeds the concentration of lactose in plasma was constant until 20 h, when it started to
338 increase rapidly. From 20 to 24-h interval, plasma lactose in MN increased by 5-fold (5.22 to
339 26.68 $\mu\text{mol/L}$; $P < 0.01$), whereas in LC it increased by only 1.5-fold (19.14 to 27.79 $\mu\text{mol/L}$;
340 $P = 0.211$), indicating that the leakiness degree is greater in MN than in LC. Generally, our
341 results showed that TJ became disrupted after 20 h of udder filling in dairy ewes. No previous
342 data are available on the timing of TJ opening during extended milking intervals in dairy
343 ewes. Similar to our results, TJ were leaky after 20 h in dairy goats (Stelwagen et al., 1994b),
344 whereas in dairy cows (Stelwagen et al. 1994a; Stelwagen et al. 1997) TJ were leaky earlier
345 (17 h), in accordance with the lower cisternal capacity in dairy cows compared with small
346 ruminants.

347 Sheep breed affected ($P < 0.01$) Na^+ and K^+ concentration in milk (Table 3). The MN
348 presented greater Na^+ concentrations (21.00 vs. 16.59 mmol/L) and lower K^+ concentration
349 (29.70 vs. 34.95 mmol/L) than LC ewes. Moreover, breed \times milking interval interaction was
350 significant ($P < 0.05$) for Na^+ concentration and the $\text{Na}^+:\text{K}^+$ ratio. Consequently, milking
351 interval only affected ($P < 0.01$) ion concentration in milk of MN ewes. In this breed, Na^+
352 concentration in milk was highest at 20- and 24-h interval, whereas K^+ concentration was
353 lowest at 24-h interval. Thus, a greater $\text{Na}^+:\text{K}^+$ ratio in the milk was observed at extended
354 milking intervals. The mineral balance between alveolar and blood compartments is
355 controlled by the presence of TJ. Therefore, the increase in Na^+ concentration and $\text{Na}^+:\text{K}^+$
356 ratio in milk of MN seems to be a consequence of TJ opening at extended milking intervals in

382 the degree of TJ leakiness differed according to the breed, being more pronounced in MN
383 than in LC ewes, probably due to differences in their udder storage capacity. It seems that
384 dairy ewes could support 20 h of udder filling without negative effects on milk yield or milk
385 composition. Further long-term studies are required.

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- 516

517 **Table 1.** Total milk yield and milk accumulation rate at different milking intervals (4, 8, 12,
 518 16, 20, and 24 h) in Manchega (MN) and Lacaune (LC) dairy ewes. ¹

Parameter	Milking interval (h)						SEM
	4	8	12	16	20	24	
Milk yield, mL							
MN	157 ^f	344 ^e	484 ^d	609 ^c	701 ^b	904 ^a	66
LC	345 ^f	761 ^e	1098 ^d	1436 ^c	1712 ^b	2012 ^a	66
Milk accumulation, mL/h							
MN	38.4 ^{ab}	42.7 ^a	40.7 ^a	38.2 ^{ab}	34.1 ^b	37.4 ^{ab}	4.5
LC	85.5 ^{bc}	95.0 ^a	91.3 ^{ab}	89.6 ^{ab}	84.6 ^c	83.9 ^c	4.5

519 ¹ Values are least square means.

520 ^{a-f} Means with different superscripts within row differ ($P < 0.05$).

521

522

523 **Table 2.** Milk composition of Manchega (MN) and Lacaune (LC) dairy ewes milked at
 524 different milking intervals.¹

Milk component	Milking intervals (h)						SEM
	4	8	12	16	20	24	
Fat, %							
MN	8.52 ^{a,x}	8.22 ^{ab,x}	8.01 ^{ab,x}	7.94 ^{bc,x}	7.58 ^{c,x}	6.97 ^{d,x}	0.23
LC	7.50 ^{a,y}	6.70 ^{b,y}	6.61 ^{b,y}	6.41 ^{b,y}	6.30 ^{b,y}	5.86 ^{c,y}	0.22
Protein, %							
MN	6.07 ^x	6.26 ^x	6.32 ^x	6.36 ^x	6.48 ^x	6.24 ^x	0.11
LC	5.68 ^y	5.59 ^y	5.68 ^y	5.68 ^y	5.73 ^y	5.59 ^y	0.11
Casein, %							
MN	4.54 ^{c,x}	4.78 ^{b,x}	4.87 ^{ab,x}	4.90 ^{ab,x}	5.02 ^{a,x}	4.81 ^{b,x}	0.09
LC	4.31 ^y	4.30 ^y	4.38 ^y	4.36 ^y	4.40 ^y	4.26 ^y	0.09
True protein, %							
MN	5.58 ^{c,x}	5.79 ^{bc,x}	5.84 ^{b,x}	5.87 ^{ab,x}	6.04 ^{a,x}	6.02 ^{ab,x}	0.12
LC	5.24 ^{abc,y}	5.07 ^{c,y}	5.37 ^{ab,y}	5.28 ^{b,y}	5.47 ^{a,y}	5.32 ^{ab,y}	0.11
Lactose, %							
MN	4.72 ^{ab}	4.76 ^{ab}	4.77 ^a	4.83 ^a	4.81 ^a	4.68 ^b	0.19
LC	4.82 ^a	4.74 ^{ab}	4.76 ^{ab}	4.72 ^{ab}	4.75 ^{ab}	4.68 ^b	0.26
Total solids, %							
MN	21.5 ^{a,x}	20.5 ^{ab,x}	20.0 ^{b,x}	20.1 ^{b,x}	19.6 ^{bc,x}	18.9 ^{c,x}	0.45
LC	18.9 ^{a,y}	17.6 ^{b,y}	17.6 ^{b,y}	17.6 ^{b,y}	17.6 ^{b,y}	17.1 ^{b,y}	0.43
SCC, log ₁₀ /ml							
MN	5.14 ^b	5.53 ^a	5.35 ^b	5.39 ^{ab}	5.32 ^b	5.23 ^b	0.10
LC	5.05 ^b	5.26 ^a	5.28 ^a	5.13 ^{ab}	5.15 ^{ab}	5.08 ^b	0.10

525 ¹ Values are least square means.

526 ^{a-c} Means with different superscripts within row differ ($P < 0.05$).

527 ^{x,y} Means with different superscripts within a column for each component differ ($P < 0.05$).

528

529

530 **Table 3.** Effect of different milking intervals (4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24 h) on the concentration
 531 of Na⁺, K⁺ and the Na⁺ to K⁺ ratio in the milk of Manchega (MN) and Lacaune (LC) breeds. ¹

Item	Milking intervals (h)						SEM
	4	8	12	16	20	24	
Na ⁺ , mmol/L							
MN	19.47 ^c	19.86 ^c	19.91 ^c	20.88 ^c	22.18 ^b	23.73 ^a	1.23
LC	16.85	16.01	16.23	17.06	16.62	16.75	1.23
K ⁺ , mmol/L							
MN	28.79 ^{bc}	30.90 ^a	30.90 ^a	29.08 ^{bc}	30.35 ^{ab}	28.41 ^c	0.97
LC	33.14	35.30	35.39	35.53	35.36	34.70	0.97
Na ⁺ :K ⁺							
MN	0.70 ^{bc}	0.65 ^c	0.66 ^c	0.76 ^b	0.76 ^b	0.86 ^a	0.05
LC	0.52	0.46	0.46	0.49	0.49	0.50	0.05

532 ¹Values are least square means.

533 ^{a-c} Means with different superscripts within row differ ($P < 0.05$).

534

535 **Figure 1.** Milk accumulation rates every four hours (0-4, 4-8, 8-12, 12-16, 16-20, 20-24 h) in
 536 Manchega (○) and Lacaune (●) dairy ewes. ^{a-c}Means within the same breed with different
 537 letters differ at $P < 0.05$. Vertical bars represent SEM.

538
 539

540 **Figure 2.** Plasmin activity at 4-, 8-, 12-, 16-, 20-, and 24-h milking interval in Manchega (○)

541 and Lacaune (●) dairy ewes. ^{a-c}Means within the same breed with different letters differ at $P <$

542 0.05. Vertical bars represent SEM.

543

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545

546 **Figure 3.** Plasma lactose concentrations obtained 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24 h after the last
 547 milking. Values are least square means \pm SEM for 8 dairy ewes of Manchega (\circ ; $n = 4$) and
 548 Lacaune (\bullet ; $n = 4$) breeds. ^{a-b}Means within the same breed with different letters differ at $P <$
 549 0.05. Vertical bars represent SEM.

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